

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 0: Introduction

Michał K. Tomczyk

Institute of Computing Science, Poznan University of Technology, Poznań, Poland

This document is part of a tutorial series on JECDM. URL: www.jecdm.cs.put.poznan.pl, email: jecdm@cs.put.poznan.pl.
The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.7.0 (Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.2).

Abstract

This document introduces the JECDM framework, explaining its objective and providing a general overview of its capabilities. It is a starting point for learning this framework.

Keywords: JECDM, introduction, features, capabilities, installation

Contents

1 Introduction	1
2 Characteristics and capabilities	1
3 On tutorials	3
4 Installation guidelines and working with own codes	3
5 On coding conventions	4
6 Overview of the modules	4

1. Introduction

This document introduces the Java framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making (JECDM). It is a computational framework written in Java that primarily intends to facilitate research on preference-based evolutionary multi-objective optimization. The document overviews JECDM's main characteristics and capabilities, discusses how it will be developed and maintained, provides installation guidelines, and briefly showcases its top-level components – modules. Overall, this document intends to help you – the reader – get acquainted with JECDM and decide whether this framework is for you.

2. Characteristics and capabilities

In this section, the general characteristics and capabilities of JECDM are discussed. They are provided in the following – loosely written and ordered – paragraphs, which occasionally

take the form of questions (FAQ).

What is the general scope of JECDM? As explained in Section 1, JECDM is a computational framework for **developing and testing preference-based evolutionary algorithms for multi-objective optimization**, with the central focus on interactive preference-learning methods [1].

Nonetheless, due to the high generalization of its components, it can be easily adapted to other tasks. For instance, its *Visualization* module can serve as a foundation for data visualization assignments that may not necessarily be related to optimization.

JECDM as a computational framework JECDM is not a pre-built software. It is a series of well-organized source codes that a researcher can use to develop and test new methods. In a nutshell, **JECDM provides a general versatile architecture**. Thus, the codes are highly generalized and structured. They follow object-oriented programming with high-level abstractions. Thus, concrete implementations – e.g., methods – emerge in JECDM as concrete parameterizations, settings, or compositions of lower-level general sources instead of being hard-coded. Additionally, the codes were designed in a way that respects computational and memory complexity, ensuring that realizations of various tasks will be highly efficient.

Overall, JECDM cannot be viewed as just a library that provides a vast spectrum of ready-to-use (but hard-coded to some extent) algorithms. Thus, if one seeks such quick programming solutions, it is not the place. Instead, as already explained – the primary focus here is on the architecture whose design provides significant capabilities regarding developing and testing. A few of the ready-to-use algorithms supplied with the initial release of JECDM are rather a proof of the concept (or examples of how to employ framework's components creatively) – not a primary purpose of this framework.

Email address: michal.tomczyk@cs.put.poznan.pl (Michał K. Tomczyk)

URL: www.cs.put.poznan.pl/mtomczyk (Michał K. Tomczyk)

How to learn JECDM? Learning architecture-oriented codes with a high level of generalization may be difficult. Presenting simple, brief pieces of code that showcase some concrete usages will not allow for comprehensive learning of the framework. Therefore, JECDM is accompanied by a series of content-rich PDF tutorial documents that cover its various aspects, starting from some core fundamentals and ending with concrete code examples.

Overall, the tutorials are starting points for learning JECDM. Nonetheless, not every possible aspect of the framework will be covered in these PDFs, as it is not reasonable to verbally describe each line of code or possible configurations of the sources. Thus, one of the fundamental prerequisites for using JECDM is that the user is a moderately skilled (at least) programmer who can read and understand someone else's codes.

What are the prerequisites? As explained above, the user is assumed to be at least a moderately skilled programmer. More specifically, the prerequisites regarding the programming skills are as follows:

- The user has comprehensive general programming knowledge and adequate skills.
- They also need to have good knowledge and skills of Java programming language.
- Additionally, algorithmics (algorithms, data structures, ensuring high computational and memory efficiency, etc.) and object-oriented programming (understanding fundamental concepts, object-oriented programming from Java programming language perspective, etc.) knowledge and skills are essential.

Furthermore, the user is assumed to be well-acquainted with such fields as:

- evolutionary (multi-objective) optimization,
- multi-criteria decision aiding (especially with preference learning),
- and their respective research methodologies.

The tutorials (and codes) **will not teach these subjects**. Furthermore, as will be explained next, the project is maintained (and will be available) in IntelliJ IDEA software. Thus, the reader should be acquainted with this IDE (although one may export the codes to other software if preferred).

About the maintenance, development, and future updates As already mentioned, the project is developed using IntelliJ IDEA software. The sources and IDE's configuration files are publicly available at GitHub: <https://github.com/MTomczyk/JECDM>. Future updates will be rare but relatively significant. Note that JECDM results from my dedication to the joint field of evolutionary multi-objective optimization and multi-criteria decision aiding, **but it is not a financially supported project**.

Thus, it will not be constantly supervised. Instead, the future updates will result from **realizations of my other projects**.

Worth mentioning here is also the API. In this framework, it is delineated only roughly, and it is not guaranteed that it will not be altered in the future. The rationale for the former is that restricting access to various components (e.g., due to imposing strict standardizations) was unwanted to give the research freedom in experimentation. This framework is for research, which – fundamentally – should not be limited by any means. Note that, however, the codes are designed so that it is relatively easy to understand the overall structurization of the sources (i.e., understand what can be considered API and what not). Thus, they are also prepared for “non-colliding” future updates – as long as the user will not perform significant modifications of the framework's elements. However, they can feel free (and should) to do so if they believe it will positively impact their studies.

On self-sufficiency Worth noting is that the framework was designed to be self-sufficient to a large extent. Thus, the number of third-party libraries is reduced to a bare minimum, and thus, JECDM relies mainly on Java programming language. Note that only a few external libraries have been explicitly pre-selected and incorporated into this project. They are stored in an auxiliary “libs” folder. The framework relies solely on free-to-use libraries that can be incorporated as a part of other projects. As instructed, their licenses and license notices accompany these libraries.

Why Java programming language? JECDM intends to provide a versatile architecture for conducting algorithmics-oriented studies. Satisfying objectives imposed by software engineering contradicts – to some extent – the general goals delineated by practitioners of algorithmics. Nonetheless, I believe Java represents a satisfactory compromise of these two programming worlds. First, it is an excellent language for maintaining huge codes developed in the spirit of software engineering. Second, Java virtual machines are fast nowadays, ensuring satisfactory runtime performance. Also, Java provides many means to optimize the codes from a formal perspective. Naturally, Java is not the best option when formal memory optimization or direct memory access is required. However, this is not the case in my projects. Thus, Java is the language that best satisfies my requirements. Overall, it allows me to develop and maintain well-designed codes – even of significant size – that follow good practices of object-oriented programming and respect computational efficiency. Lastly, another benefit of Java is that it is platform-independent, which may be convenient on various levels, e.g., when sharing applications built using JECDM (or sharing the framework itself).

On capabilities The general capabilities of JECDM are linked to its top-level modules, which will be briefly overviewed in the following sections. As for now, they can be summarized as follows:

- JECDM provides versatile visualization tools that can be

employed in various contexts.

- The framework delivers a module dedicated to evolutionary computation, with a central focus on multi-objective optimization.
- Further, it introduces a module for multi-criteria decision aiding – primarily developed for implementing interactive preference-learning processes.
- Finally, JECDM delivers a flexible tool for creating and executing extensive experiments.

Is JECDM free to use? Yes, JECDM is free to use, and its versions from before v1.7.0 were licensed under CC BY 4.0. Since v1.7.0, JECDM uses the MIT license.

Important note: The software is free to use, but one uses it at their own risk.

How to acknowledge the project? It is requested to give an appropriate credit to JECDM’s author (me) if using this software. Since JECDM is primarily for research, appropriate credit can be a citation. As for the initial release of JECDM, one can cite, e.g., this document in the following way:

Tomczyk, M. (2024). *Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making. Tutorial 0: Introduction.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14283750>.

Note that, however, a peer-reviewed publication showcasing JECDM is planned to be published soon. When issued, it is suggested to cite that future work (this paragraph will be accordingly updated in the future). When using JECDM for commercial purposes, appropriate credit should also be given.

3. On tutorials

As already explained in Section 2, one can learn JECDM by reading accompanying tutorials. The initial release of the framework is supplied with 6 such documents (including this one):

1. Tutorial 0: Introduction;
2. Tutorial 1: Visualization module;
3. Tutorial 2: Evolutionary Computation module – part 1: Basics and single-objective optimization;
4. Tutorial 3: Evolutionary Computation module – part 2: Multi-objective optimization;
5. Tutorial 4: Decision Support module;
6. Tutorial 5: Experimentation module.

The above documents can be considered fundamental starting points, and users must familiarize themselves with them first (**in the given order**). These tutorials are linked to the core modules of this framework. **Note that** new tutorials supplied along with updates can be expected in the future.

Apart from giving a general insight into JECDM, these PDF tutorials also provide concrete examples of how to use the framework’s various components in practice. These examples are accompanied by respective source codes that are stored and cataloged in the *Tutorials* module (see Figure 1 that portrays its initial structure). When PDF’s section (or subsection, etc.)

Figure 1: *Tutorials* module

concerns such a code example, it will be highlighted twofold:

- The section title will end with “[T]” suffix (*T* stands for “tutorial”).
- The section will begin with a rectangular box with a gray background that provides a path to the tutorial’s source codes. The box will look like the one below:

Source package: *example path*

As for an illustrative example, Figure 2 illustrates a snippet of the table of contents of the document entitled *Tutorial 1: Visualization module* (notice the [T] suffixes), while Figure 3 illustrates the first section of this document that provides a concrete use case of JECDM.

Finally, let me note that all the tutorial documents share the same layout. Importantly, the document’s header includes relevant information on JECDM’s version used when preparing the tutorial (as well as the version of Java and IDE). For instance, this document’s header states that: *The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.0 (initial release; Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.2).*

4. Installation guidelines and working with own codes

The installation of JECDM is relatively simple. As explained, the source codes, project configurations, and other relevant files are shared on a public GitHub repository: <https://github.com>.

Contents	
1	Introduction 2
2	Understanding fundamental concepts 2
2.1	The multilevel data processing 2
2.2	A brief discussion on the queuing system 2
2.3	Understanding display ranges (manager) 3
2.4	Understanding data sets 5
2.5	General overview of the hierarchy of the highest-level GUI components 6
3	General plot for 2D visualization 7
3.1	Creating and displaying a plot [T] 7
3.2	Basics on creating and uploading a data set (fixed display ranges) [T] 8
3.3	Using dynamic display ranges [T] 10
3.4	Drawing continuous lines [T] 10
3.5	Introducing breaks into rendered lines [T] 10
3.6	Establishing a custom display ranges mapping [T] 11
3.7	Using multiple data sets and enabling the legend [T] 12
3.8	Customizing the legend [T] 13
3.9	Using gradients [T] 14
3.10	Gradient customization [T] 15
3.11	Creating a colorbar and using a non-coordinate-dependent gradient [T] 17
3.12	Turning off drawing area clipping [T] 19
3.13	Examining marker style configurations [T] 19
3.14	Using nonlinear scales [T] 19

Figure 2: Example table of contents

3.1. Creating and displaying a plot [T]

Source package:
`t1.t10.t1.visualization.module.t1_plot2d.t1`

This short (few lines of code; see Listing 5) tutorial explains how to create an empty 2D plot and how to display it. It also shows some basic customization options (e.g., turning off the axes). The expected window displayed when executing the program (executing the “main” method) is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The expected window containing the empty plot

Figure 3: Example tutorial (use case)

[com/MTomczyk/JECM](https://github.com/MTomczyk/JECM). Thus, the user can clone the project to IntelliJ IDEA and use it as it is (the IDE should automatically configure everything; obviously, a proper Java version should be installed before uploading the project). For instructions on cloning into IntelliJ IDEA, the user is referred to its developer’s website, which contains helpful tutorials. Building the project

and executing all tests once cloned (modules have their test resource roots) is also recommended.

Alternatively, pre-built jars are available on the project’s home page. They are self-sufficient, in a sense that they contained extracted external dependencies (libraries). Note that, however, they exclude the Tutorials and Projects modules, only the core modules are included (see Section 6).

Regarding the source code, please note that the project is developed linearly by a single developer, and updates will be relatively infrequent. Thus, fetching and updating the project (equivalent to moving to newer versions) will be somewhat straightforward. However, users are advised to work on their projects separately from the JECM’s main branch and modules. It is recommended, e.g., to work in one’s own module (s), thus treating – in some sense – the JECM’s sources as a separate jar. For instance, the module named Private has already been marked as being ignored by Git. I use it as a sandbox area, i.e., for developing new pieces of code. I assume the Private module is considered at the top of the project’s module hierarchy (Private can import sources from other modules but not vice-versa). It is recommended to use a similar development approach and work in your own Private module (gitignored). This way, the risk of inconsistencies in future updates may be somewhat alleviated (as already explained, the framework’s API is only roughly delineated, and it is not guaranteed that it will not change in the future). Finally, users may also work with their external libraries this way – include them in the module at the module’s level.

5. On coding conventions

The source codes follow commonly used coding conventions. Thus, they are relatively easy to read. Note that, however, a few used style-related decisions made by me – that may be deemed less common – are listed below for convenience:

- Class fields begin with ‘_’ prefix and *this*. reference is not used to access them for brevity.
- The names of interfaces begin with ‘I’ prefixes.
- The names of abstract classes begin with ‘Abstract’ prefixes.
- Classes requiring relatively extensive parameterization can often be instantiated by passing the relevant parameters to the constructor via an instance of an inner static class named Params (often called *params container* in the tutorials).

6. Overview of the modules

This section briefly overviews the JECM’s modules. Note that they constitute a hierarchy that is illustrated in Figure 4. The modules can be divided into two self-explanatory categories: *core* and *extras*. Let us start the discussion with the core modules, starting from the bottom and moving up.

Figure 4: The hierarchy of the modules

Utils. This module is the lowest in the hierarchy. It contains sources with various purposes, e.g., representing custom data structures, having statistics-related functionalities, or being random number generators. Overall, there are not enough sources to emerge among these functions, e.g., a dedicated module. Thus, they are kept in this auxiliary lowest-level place.

Visualization. This module provides various visualization tools implemented almost from scratch. They offer two modes of rendering: 2D (based on Java Swing) and 3D (based on OpenGL). Note that this module was designed to make it easy to be coupled with higher-level modules, e.g., for evolutionary computation. A detailed tutorial on this module is *Tutorial 1: Visualization module* document. Figures 5 and 6 illustrate example rendering products obtained using this module’s tools.

DecisionSupport. The following module is dedicated to multi-criteria decision aiding. It primarily delivers a systematic approach to implementing a decision-reaching system. It includes various steps relevant to this field, e.g., preference elicitation or preference modeling. A comprehensive tutorial on this module can be found in *Tutorial 4: Decision Support module* document.

EvolutionaryComputation. This module concerns designing and testing evolutionary methods for single- and multi-objective optimization. It delivers source codes that highly generalize the concept of evolutionary processing by representing it as a series of sequentially executed processing blocks that designed methods may freely adapt. Thus, concrete algorithmic implementations can emerge from the abstract implementation by suitably adjusting the processing. This way, high-level code reusability is ensured, and new, creatively designed methods may be developed relatively quickly.

Note that the initial release of JECM includes a few preselected and well-known algorithms from the stream of (preference-based) evolutionary multi-objective optimization,

primarily to showcase how to utilize the module when creating one’s own methods. The detailed tutorials on this module can be found in two documents: *Tutorial 2: Evolutionary Computation module – part 1: Basics and single-objective optimization* and *Tutorial 3: Evolutionary Computation module – part 2: Multi-objective optimization*.

Note that the module was designed to be easily coupled with the *Visualization* one. As an example, Figure 7 illustrates an example progression of an *interactive* (preference-based) IEMO/D algorithm [2] that progressively learns the decision maker’s preferences and accordingly leads the evolved population towards preferred Pareto optimal solutions (note that the visualization concerns all populations generated throughout evolution; they are illustrated using different colors obtained from a gradient).

Experimentation. The last “core” module was designed to allow for testing the methods developed using the preceding modules – primarily preference-based evolutionary methods for multi-objective optimization. It allows for relatively quick creation of experimental setups (even those considered massive). Importantly, their execution (i.e., performing the experiments) is relatively efficient. Finally, the module provides various means for post-processing the results to derive valuable conclusions (e.g., via performing cross-examination or statistical tests). Comprehensive tutorials on this practical module can be found in *Tutorial 5: Experimentation module* document.

Tutorials and Projects. Finally, these highest-level modules belong to the “Extras” category. First, *Tutorials*, as already explained, contains source codes that accompany the practical use cases presented in the tutorial documents. Second, *Projects* module stores (will store) the source codes of my future research projects, which I will be willing to share with the community.

References

- [1] Kadziński, M., Tervonen, T., 2013. Stochastic ordinal regression for multiple criteria sorting problems. *Decision Support Systems* 55, 55–66. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2012.12.030>.
- [2] Tomczyk, M.K., Kadziński, M., 2020. Decomposition-based interactive evolutionary algorithm for multiple objective optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 24, 320–334. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2019.2915767>.

Figure 5: Example 2D parallel coordinate plot

Figure 6: Example 3D heatmap

Figure 7: Example convergence of the IEMO/D algorithm (populations constructed throughout generations)